
Superintelligence Challenges and Existential Risks

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Abstract

As artificial intelligence (AI) nears human-level performance in more complex cognitive tasks ([Bubeck et al., 2023](#); [Chollet, 2025](#)), it becomes increasingly urgent to consider what may happen once AI surpasses the most intelligent humans. Artificial superintelligence (ASI) may seem distant, but accelerating progress in AI ([Krizhevsky et al., 2012](#); [Vaswani et al., 2017](#); [Kaplan et al., 2020](#); [OpenAI, 2022-2026](#)) suggests it could arrive sooner than many anticipate. Given the asymmetrical risks posed by underestimating the rate of future progress, we start by outlining why one might cautiously expect ASI to be developed between 2029 and 2033. We then contend that existential risks may increase significantly during the development and deployment of ASI, such that through the 2030s, existential risk may reach its highest levels since the 1960s. In response, we introduce Superintelligence Challenges and Existential Risks as a framework for ASI risk management, where we focus on global challenges entailed by ASI, and map out failure modes traceable to each. We examine five main ASI challenges (technical safety, concentration of power, international governance, social health, and ethical challenges) where critical failure of any could result in catastrophic or existential risks. Our goal is to begin grounding ASI existential risks in a minimal set of overarching challenges that seem unavoidable.

1. Introduction

AGI → ASI

Artificial general intelligence (AGI) is a broad term defined here as an autonomous AI that outperforms humans at most economic work ([OpenAI, n.d.](#)) and therefore could presumably automate a large fraction of human labor ([Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2018](#)).

However, many have noted that an AI this capable may be short-lived ([Bostrom, 2014](#); [Yudkowsky, 2013](#)), in that if an AI could automate scientific research ([Lu et al., 2024](#)) and machine learning engineering ([Chan et al., 2024](#)), then it could seemingly automate AI R&D as well (e.g. [Owen, 2024](#)). If so, given the relative speed of computers, this might allow an AGI to iteratively improve its own design in rapid loops, leading to an ‘intelligence explosion’ ([Good, 1965](#)). The expected end result would be an artificial superintelligence (ASI), defined here as an AI that outperforms the most intelligent humans in virtually all cognitive domains ([Bostrom, 2014](#)). While superintelligence may be technically feasible by other means, an intelligence explosion is likely the fastest scenario to weigh when intending not to underestimate future rates of change.

As a general-purpose technology, advanced AI implies both unique risks ([Bengio et al., 2024](#)) and rewards ([Altman, 2023](#)). Many argue that ASI specifically would initiate a technological singularity ([Ulam, 1958](#); [Vinge, 1993](#)), or a period of extremely compressed technological progress, which could in theory produce timely solutions for major issues like climate change. Simultaneously, many warn that ASI would pose existential risks ([CAIS, 2023](#)), defined here as risks that threaten human extinction, or irreversible damage to humanity’s long-term future ([Bostrom 2013](#); [Ord 2020](#)). Natural risks like asteroid collisions may be random, but as technology becomes more powerful, humanity’s capacity to destroy itself continues to grow, as with nuclear weapons ([Bostrom, 2002](#)), bioweapons ([Millett & Snyder-Beattie, 2017](#)), and AI ([CAIS, 2023](#)). This makes the need to mitigate man-made existential risks paramount. While this may still seem remote for AI, the CEOs of many AI firms have expressed interest in AI accelerating scientific discovery ([Altman, 2024](#); [Amodei, 2024](#)). This would presumably include accelerating AI research, which

may lead to an intelligence explosion. Industry leaders have also predicted since 2023 that an AGI-like system could arrive soon ([Amodei, 2024](#); [Huang, 2024](#); [Legg, 2023](#)).

Public Research

AI researchers have envisioned superintelligent machines since the field's earliest days ([Turing, 1951](#)). Yet despite the impact one might expect from ASI, relatively few have explored the subject in depth ([Bostrom, 2014](#); [Hendrycks et al., 2025](#); [Kokotajlo et al., 2025](#)). Since ASI is still regarded as highly futuristic by most, skepticism and more immediate concerns likely explain this. However, in 2023, safety researchers predicted superintelligence could arrive by 2030 ([Leike et al., 2023](#)). In 2024, a new company was founded with the explicit mission of building safe ASI ([Sutskever et al., 2024](#)). In 2025, companies started becoming more direct about ASI as their vision (e.g. [Altman, 2025](#); [Amodei, 2024](#); [Metz & Isaac, 2025](#)). This trend suggests that despite its broader perception as deeply theoretical, ASI could soon become reality. Given that ASI stands to permeate every discipline, its trajectory requires attention from not only researchers, but also policymakers, professionals, and the broader public. Lastly, while some have explored the risks of AI these explorations generally focus on specific risks (e.g. technical safety or geopolitics). It is rare for a paper to explore the comprehensive space of ASI existential risks within a single cohesive framework (e.g. [Hendrycks et al., 2023](#)), leaving a research gap that this work intends to help fill.

Limited Awareness

Superintelligence is still relatively unknown, and discussion about existential risks in general is uncommon. The competitive pressures ([Armstrong et al., 2016](#)) and extensive scope ([AI Index Report, 2024](#)) of AI specifically also pose challenges. Given that ASI could offer long-term competitive advantages ([Amodei, 2025](#)) as well as pose extreme risks ([Bengio et al., 2024](#)), these stakes may create incentives for limited public disclosure. Many employees at AI companies have also signed confidentiality agreements ([Milmo, 2024](#)) that further reduce public disclosure about AI risks ([Hilton et al., 2024](#)). Compounding this, given AI's broad scope, discussions on ASI risks that do arise may splinter and emphasize divergent concerns, such as technical safety, social inequality, or geopolitics. If not considered together as part of a broader cohesive plan, these can further divide the limited conversation about large-scale AI risks.

Commercial Incentives

To discuss superintelligence candidly, however, one must also note the commercial incentives surrounding current AI development. Given that AI is largely a private-sector endeavor ([Cihon et al., 2021](#)), profit motive¹ may present a conflict of interest ([Slee, 2020](#)), and among other risks, may further entrench corporate power ([Hendrycks et al., 2023](#)). For AI businesses seeking to raise capital, attract talent, or market their products, commercial pressures may favor not fully publicizing the most severe AI risks. One might reasonably assume, however, that the scale of investment in AI reflects the scale of its risks, and there has been enormous corporate investment in AI, including multiple \$500 billion infrastructure plans in the U.S. alone ([Nvidia, 2025](#); [OpenAI, 2025](#)). By comparison, ~\$100 billion was spent globally on nuclear weapons in 2024 ([ICAN, 2025](#)). At first sight, a technology poised to be more powerful than nuclear weapons may be developed primarily by for-profit corporations. Whether this trend continues remains uncertain. Given the national security implications of superintelligence ([Hendrycks et al., 2025](#)), it is plausible that nation-states could assume control of its development ([Aschenbrenner, 2024](#)), as they did with nuclear weapons in the 20th century.

¹ AI companies may intend to avoid influence from profits, but competitive pressures and the need for resources at scale can force compromises. OpenAI started as a nonprofit ([OpenAI, 2015](#)), but converted to a 'capped-profit' in 2019 to raise more capital ([OpenAI, 2019](#)).

2. Background

Technical Feasibility

From first principles, the human brain shows that general intelligence is physically possible, and there is little reason to suspect that the brain has reached the physical limits of cognitive performance, i.e. it could theoretically be faster, larger, have more reliable memory, etc. ([von Neumann, 1958](#)). The argument follows there is then little reason to anticipate a ceiling at human-level cognition, especially when considering the physical advantages of digital systems, including speed ([von Neumann, 1958](#)), precision ([Faisal et al., 2008](#)), scalability ([Kaplan et al., 2020](#)), memory sharing, and perhaps most importantly, being both instantly copyable and modifiable ([Bostrom, 2014](#)). Beyond theory, there is also evidence of machines cognitively outperforming humans in narrower domains, and these moments often surprise people when they occur real-time. Prior to 1997, many believed AI could not beat humans in chess ([Knight, 2021](#)). Many similarly thought it would take much longer before it happened with Go in 2016 ([Silver et](#)

al., 2016). As such, these moments have already demonstrated that there is substantial room for improvement beyond the highest performing humans in cognitive competitions. These were still combinatorial games, but now as AI steadily improves in more general skills like writing, coding, and math, there stand to be fewer exception cases where humans cognitively outperform AI. From this trend, one might infer that in the limit case, superintelligence would be the eventual instance where there remain virtually no more exceptions of humans outperforming AI in cognitive tasks.

Scale of Investment

AI is attracting major investment from many of the world's wealthiest individuals (e.g. [Wirz, 2025](#)). The high valuations of AI research labs reflect this, e.g. Safe Superintelligence Inc. was founded in 2024, and is reportedly already valued at \$32B ([Apr 2025](#)). Meanwhile, at the time of writing, OpenAI is reportedly valued at \$850B ([Apr 2026](#)), Anthropic at \$950B ([Feb 2026](#)), and xAI at \$250B ([Apr, 2026](#)). Presented alone, however, these numbers can be misleading, as these AI startups often have relationships with much larger U.S. companies, e.g. Microsoft, Amazon, and Tesla. These companies vie for AI market share with Alphabet (Google), Meta, and Apple over AI infrastructure largely designed by Nvidia and Broadcom and produced by TSMC. Together, these nine firms are valued at ~\$23T ([CompaniesMarketCap, 2026](#)) compared to the U.S. GDP of ~\$31T ([JEC, 2025](#)) and frequently represent nine of the ten largest companies in the world by stock price. Expenditures also shed light on AI's priority: it may seem surprising that Meta was reportedly offering \$100M bonuses to recruit talent from OpenAI ([Reuters, 2025](#)), but when one considers Meta planned \$65B in capital expenditures for AI projects in 2025 ([Singh, 2025](#)), \$100M seems more reasonable. Despite the investment attracted, as well as forecasts of ASI ([Leike et al., 2023](#); [Sutskever et al., 2024](#); [Kokotajlo, 2025](#)), whistleblower warnings ([Hilton et al., 2024](#)), leadership fallout ([OpenAI, 2023](#)), and high-profile resignations (e.g. [Morris, 2024](#); [Goldman, 2024](#)), there is relatively little discussion about preparing for AI existential risks.

Media Coverage

A summary of the current AI landscape often portrayed in the U.S. is that companies are racing to build AGI, often described as an AI capable of human-level intelligence (e.g. [O'Brien, 2024](#)). Online

subcultures may home in on superintelligence more directly, but presenting AGI as the end goal is common in media coverage of AI. However, assuming progress does not halt there, then the longer-term goal naturally shifts to ASI and exceeding humans. Some may view this difference as merely semantic, but given the existential risks of ASI specifically, this distinction likely warrants more direct public emphasis. While many industry leaders have not publicly alluded to superintelligence, many have, as comments about ASI have become more frequent since 2023 (**Table 1**).

Shifting Baselines

A psychological phenomenon that may tend towards underestimating the rate of future progress² is a tendency that humans have to readjust expectations or shift baselines ([Soga & Gaston, 2018](#)). If a random observer in 2020 were shown that in 2025, AI can write and program ([OpenAI, 2024](#)), interpret audio and images ([OpenAI, 2024](#)), and generate realistic video and music ([OpenAI, 2024](#); [Suno, 2024](#)), this would have almost certainly greatly exceeded most people's expectations. However, as AI now begins to solve more complex problems ([OpenAI, 2025](#)) and show early signs of autonomy ([Anthropic, 2024](#); [Google, 2025](#)), expectations have since shifted. With rapid progress being normalized, much public attention is instead drawn to copyright lawsuits (e.g. [Allyn, 2025](#)), stock values, and limitations of current systems (e.g. [NPR, 2025](#)). While important, these likely obscure more fundamental implications, like the seeming acceleration of AI as a field, or the field's generally anticipated end state. As progress continues, new technical baselines also arise, where the benchmarks used to assess AI performance now include PhD-level expertise ([Rein et al., 2023](#)), math and coding competitions ([OpenAI, 2024](#); [Chervonyi et al., 2025](#)), automated machine learning ([Chan et al., 2024](#)), and "Humanity's Last Exam" ([Phan et al., 2025](#)). These various tests extend well beyond the abilities of most humans, yet due to current limitations such as reliability ([Asgari et al., 2025](#)), many may still maintain that AI is still not at human-level intelligence, especially from an economic perspective.

² AI performance is already being evaluated in highly competitive fields. For example, AI-generated code is compared to code from developers who have enrolled in coding competitions ([OpenAI, 2024](#)). Comparisons for at least entry-level performance can also be found in medicine ([Google, 2023](#)), law ([OpenAI, 2023](#)), and math ([Google, 2024](#)). Given that by 2026, AI is already being compared to at least early professionals in multiple competitive domains, one may underestimate how near AI is to surpassing humans in many fields at once, particularly in the event of an intelligence explosion.

Table 1, Leaders Recognize Superintelligence: Public references to superintelligence from industry leaders.

<p><i>"Superintelligent AIs are in our future. Compared to a computer, our brains operate at a snail's pace: An electrical signal in the brain moves at 1/100,000th the speed of the signal in a silicon chip!"</i> — Bill Gates, Co-Founder and former CEO of Microsoft (Mar 2023)</p> <p><i>"I think it's quite conceivable that humanity is just a passing phase in the evolution of intelligence."</i> <i>"I think we're moving into a period when for the first time ever we may have things more intelligent than us."</i> — Geoff Hinton, former researcher at Google (May 2023, Jun 2024)</p> <p><i>"Superintelligence will be the most impactful technology humanity has ever invented, and could help us solve many of the world's most important problems. But the vast power of superintelligence could also be very dangerous, and could lead to the disempowerment of humanity or even human extinction. While superintelligence seems far off now, we believe it could arrive this decade. [...] Currently, we don't have a solution for steering or controlling a potentially superintelligent AI, and preventing it from going rogue."</i> — Jan Leike et al., researcher at Anthropic (Jul 2023)</p> <p><i>"The highest level in our matrix in terms of combined performance and generality is ASI (Artificial Superintelligence). We define 'Superhuman' performance as outperforming 100% of humans."</i> — Meredith Morris et al., researchers at Google DeepMind (Nov 2023)</p> <p><i>"SoftBank Group has done many things until now that have all been a warmup for my great dream to realize artificial superintelligence."</i> — Masayoshi Son, Founder, Chairman, & CEO of SoftBank (Jun 2024)</p> <p><i>"Superintelligence is within reach. Building safe superintelligence (SSI) is the most important technical problem of our time. We have started the world's first straight-shot SSI lab, with one goal and one product: a safe superintelligence."</i> <i>"I want to talk a little bit about superintelligence, just a bit—because that is obviously where this field is headed."</i> — Ilya Sutskever et al., Co-Founder of Safe Superintelligence Inc. (SSI), Co-Founder at OpenAI (Jun 2024, Dec 2024)</p> <p><i>"I think really what all the AI companies are aiming to build is digital superintelligence. So, you know, intelligence that's far smarter than any human—and then ultimately, an intelligence that's far smarter than all humans combined."</i> <i>"It is increasingly likely that AI will superset the intelligence of any single human by the end of 2025 and maybe all humans by 2027/2028. Probability that AI exceeds the intelligence of all humans combined by 2030 is ~100%."</i> — Elon Musk, CEO of Tesla & SpaceX, Co-Founder of xAI, OpenAI, Neuralink, SpaceX, Owner of X (Jul 2024 @ 28:00, Dec 2024)</p> <p><i>"I think [powerful AI] could come as early as 2026, though there are also ways it could take much longer. [...] In terms of pure intelligence, it is smarter than a Nobel Prize winner across most relevant fields [...] We could summarize this as a 'country of geniuses in a datacenter'."</i> — Dario Amodei, Co-Founder and CEO of Anthropic, former VP of research at OpenAI (Oct 2024)</p> <p><i>"Right now, let's say there's between 10-20 billion dollars of LLM-based revenue. If you believe that we're actually on a track towards superintelligence or AGI, then it stands to reason that that's going to go to a trillion dollars or more revenue [...] over who knows how many years—I tend to believe a fewer number of years. I think we're sort of in the 2-4 range."</i> — Alexandr Wang, Co-Founder and CEO of Scale AI, (Jan 2025)</p> <p><i>"It is possible that we will have superintelligence in a few thousand days (!); it may take longer, but I'm confident we'll get there."</i> <i>"We are now confident we know how to build AGI as we have traditionally understood it. [...] We are beginning to turn our aim beyond that, to superintelligence in the true sense of the word. [...] We're pretty confident that in the next few years, everyone will see what we see [...]"</i> <i>"OpenAI is a lot of things now, but before anything else, we are a superintelligence research company."</i> — Sam Altman, Co-Founder and CEO of OpenAI (Sep 2024, Jan 2025, Jun 2025)</p>
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Historical Precedent

Historically speaking, nuclear weapons provide a valuable precedent for technology posing existential risks, particularly as a timeline. In 1939, the discovery of nuclear fission ([Meitner & Frisch, 1939](#)) sparked a global race between nations to successfully weaponize nuclear physics. Even still, it took six years during World War II before nuclear weapons were developed and used in 1945. Development continued following the war. By 1952, thermonuclear warheads 1000x stronger were created, yielding 10-megatons, and by 1955, multiple nations had tested thermonuclear weapons ([Rhodes, 1995](#)). Given that a later analysis suggested the fallout of even 100-megatons detonated over major urban centers could have serious climatic

consequences ([Turco et al., 1983](#)), one might then argue it took 16 years (1939-1955) before nuclear weapons R&D posed risks on an existential scale. With this in mind, if the release of ChatGPT in 2022 was the analogous proof-of-concept that sparked the global AGI race, it would then be preceded to see powerful new AI weapons by 2028, and AI as an existential risk by 2038. Rather, given the differences in time and technology, this timeline may be conservative. AI may develop much more quickly, particularly with existential risks, given differences such as AI's immense economic potential ([Chui et al., 2023](#)), the availability of modern computers and the Internet to hasten R&D ([Seigel, 1997](#)), and that unlike nuclear weapons, better AI can iteratively help develop better AI ([Good, 1965](#)).

Risks of Speaking Out

Employees at AI companies have raised the issue of AI whistleblower protections (Hilton et al., 2024). With unprecedented power at stake with ASI, one would be wise not to underestimate what actions global powers may take to win the AI arms race. This may lead to significant pressure placed on AI whistleblowers who raise safety, legal, or ethical concerns. Many tactics might in theory be used against AI whistleblowers and activists, such as intimidation, blacklisting, reputational attacks, legal aggression, and more (e.g. Garrick & Buck, 2020).

3. Foundational Arguments

Our investigation into ASI existential risks is driven by the following broad research questions:

Question 1: What seemingly inevitable challenges for ASI, if mishandled, make it difficult to envision a positive long-term future for humanity?

Question 2: Among the various ASI challenges (Q1), how do we prioritize them?

It is best practice in problem solving to first ensure that the problem itself is well-defined. For the problem of avoiding ASI existential risks, we investigate these research objectives within the context of three initial arguments that provide important background for framing the risk framework. These arguments capture a specific sequence of events that we broadly anticipate regardless of outcome, and thereby provide a strong starting point for planning:

Claim #1, AGI Is Near: AGI (definitions may vary) seems inevitable and likely to arrive relatively soon.

Claim #2, AGI → ASI: AGI would likely be used to improve its own design and develop ASI.

Claim #3, ASI → Existential Risks: ASI would pose existential risks.

These arguments help us define how ASI will most likely be developed, why existential risks would arise, how much time before ASI is developed, etc. These arguments therefore provide implicit structure in terms of scope, assumptions, constraints, and timeframes that our framework presumes and operates within. Any who finds all three arguments noncontentious may prefer to skip to [Framework](#), where we construct the existential risk framework.

Claim #1: AGI Is Near

Core Argument: AGI (definitions may vary) seems inevitable and likely to arrive relatively soon.

Given the major geopolitical and economic incentives for well-funded groups to pursue a technology poised to be as powerful as AGI (e.g. Schmid et al., 2025), globally halting AI development seems highly implausible. In this case, the more relevant question likely becomes not if, but when will AGI be developed? After consideration, we predict that AGI in the sense that we understand it could arrive between 2028 and 2030. Our arguments for arriving at this prediction are detailed below.

(1) A timeline prediction for AGI or ASI may miss in two directions: too early or too late. Missing too late entails greater risks.

If one considers a hypothetical distribution describing the true probability of AGI or ASI being developed over time, predicting either too early or too late would correspond to one's prediction curve being shifted left or right of the respective true curve (Figure 1). It is naturally important to remain humble when trying to predict future timelines. If one suspects then that some error in their prediction is likely, comparing the relative risks of predicting AGI or ASI too early vs. too late may help inform us which direction is overall lower risk to err towards. Given that predicting AGI too late tends towards unpreparedness, we contend that it is lower risk to predict AGI too early.

Figure 1: Predicting AGI too early (blue) is preferable to predicting ASI too late (orange) relative to a hypothetical true scenario (black).

Predicting AGI arrives too early may risk unintended consequences, but these would likely not be existential. Mistakes in these scenarios may slow or limit AI temporarily, but without AGI yet existing, these would not have the means to actuate existential risks. Meanwhile, predicting AGI too late carries more

direct existential risks due to AGI’s unexpected arrival. For example, a major existential risk that we foresee with advanced AI systems is extreme concentrations of power potentially forming. To this end, being unprepared for AGI greatly increases the risk of critical initial conditions being decided by relatively few people, which could lend itself towards power becoming entrenched. Moreover, being unprepared for AGI exacerbates humanity’s vulnerability to virtually every source of risk, whether technical, geopolitical, or social. Unregulated AI stands to be extremely volatile (e.g. [Bengio et al., 2024](#)). New international regulations are likely needed to prevent conflict over AGI (e.g. [Robinson, 2025](#)), as well as new social programs to support workers who may be displaced by AI (e.g. [UNDP, 2025](#)), as layoffs from technology companies have already started (e.g. [Bellan, 2025](#)). Given AI’s reliance on data, data privacy laws and related consumer protection measures likely require updates (e.g. [Sadek et al., 2024](#)). These are only a small fraction of what seem necessary for AGI. Failure to be prepared on such fronts reasonably risks major social unrest.

Given these significant asymmetries in risk, if some error in one’s AGI timeline prediction is more likely than not, then we opt to err towards the lower-risk stance of predicting AGI too early (**Figure 1**). Of the

two options, this appears as the preferable path to minimize the probability of AI existential risks.

(2) We hypothesize that overall, progress in AI is accelerating.

AI has historically been a field of summer and winter cycles dating back to the 1950s ([Toosi et al., 2021](#)). However, progress accelerated greatly in 2012 with the rise of neural networks ([Krizhevsky et al., 2012](#)), and has seemingly not slowed since. Given that the majority of recent progress in AI has built off deep learning (e.g. [LeCun et al., 2015](#)), one might consider how many breakthroughs or key moments have happened in AI since 2012 as a coarse measure of how the field has progressed since. What constitutes a breakthrough or key moment is naturally subjective. Here, we focus on moments where (1) a paradigm-defining technique was introduced that is actively used in frontier models today, or (2) new major capabilities or approaches to AI development were successfully demonstrated at scale. One might then differentiate the transformer ([Vaswani et al., 2017](#)) as a paradigm-defining technique (1) from BERT ([Devlin et al., 2018](#)) as its first major application at scale (2). Under these two criteria, we identify 15 breakthrough or key moments in AI spanning from 2012 to 2025 (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2, Timeline of Breakthrough Moments in AI (2012-2025): Timeline of key or breakthrough moments in AI spanning from 2012 through 2025. 2020s show higher frequency of moments than 2010s. Not shown due to limited space but also a breakthrough was the development of diffusion models ([Ho et al., 2020](#)).

As shown in **Figure 2**, the rate of breakthrough moments in AI appears to have increased from the 2010s to the 2020s. The vast progress of AI models

through the 2020s reflects this. For reference, it is worth recalling that in 2020, it was considered state-of-the-art for a large language model (LLM) to do 3-

digit arithmetic, basic translation, and use a novel word in a sentence (Brown et al., 2020). Today, LLMs now compete in math and coding competitions (OpenAI, 2024), can respond in 100+ languages (Barkley, 2024), and pass graduate-level exams (e.g. Stribling et al., 2024), thus profoundly impacting higher education. Most importantly, one might consider what this steep progress curve implies for AI models in 2030. Overall, we see compelling evidence to presume that progress in AI is accelerating. Recalling our earlier intention of not underestimating future progress, we note that accelerating growth rates are infamously easy to underestimate (e.g. Wagenaar & Sagaria, 1975). This might make one particularly cautious about dismissing aggressive AGI or ASI timelines as unrealistic, as accelerating progress may be difficult to comprehend and forecast.

(3) We expect progress in AI to continue accelerating for the near future.

Just as the slope of a function at a point in time can be more predictive of future values than the value itself, even if AI models now are unimpressive to some, the fact that progress seems to be accelerating would suggest that future models could rapidly improve. Beyond theoretical curves, we also have specific reasons to suspect AI will continue accelerating in the near future. First, as we explore in **Argument #2**, assuming AI is physically capable of completing AI R&D tasks, then barring regulation, automation of AI R&D to boost productivity seems almost inevitable. Accordingly, we expect to see gradual automation of various ML tasks now done by humans, creating a strong R&D feedback loop over time that could greatly accelerate the rate of AI progress. Second, the economic returns of AI have been relatively modest relative to its investment (e.g. Sukharevsky et al., 2025). We suspect that this is temporary and that there will be a major shift once autonomy is unlocked. Once the challenges of AI autonomy are solved to the extent that AI agents are robust enough to create real-world value (i.e. be able to act as a remote worker), we would then expect to see a massive influx of further investment in AI. Third, we expect the global AI race may further intensify (Hendrycks et al., 2025), adding further geopolitical pressure placed on top of these other forces. For these reasons, we expect progress in AI will continue accelerating in the near future.

(4) There are still practical, real-world limitations to overcome to achieve AGI.

While progress is accelerating, there still appears significant progress necessary before true AGI is

achieved, namely regarding autonomy, reliability, and scale. Regarding autonomy, in 2026, early agents exist, but they are limited in their real-world value due to difficulty with interfaces, public trust, and other constraints. Similarly, even once AI agents are less constrained, it may take several years to improve their reliability to the point of real-world value. And then, even once autonomy and reliability are improved, it may take more time still before AI agents achieve the scale of impact expected for AGI (i.e. successful demos are not the same as ubiquitous, fully-fledged, real-world AI agents). For all these practical reasons, we plan for 2028 to 2030 as our AGI timeline. This prediction presumes the accelerating progress described but still leaves room for a few years before AI agents are truly solved. In terms of some markers we might look for, AGI would correspond to the year when the public collectively realizes the implications of AI, similar to March 2020 with COVID-19. Unemployment may start to rise, and discussion about universal basic income or a similar measure may become more urgent. There may be more public statements on AI from world leaders, as AI would likely become the central topic of public discussion, and the key issue heading into elections. While not part of the formal definition of AGI, these are some markers we would look for that may signal it has arrived.

Realistically, however, AGI will likely not be a single watershed moment, but a gradient of potentially contested stages, such that timelining AGI may be arbitrary. This is particularly true if the performance of AGI becomes heavily dependent on the amount of compute used to achieve certain results. We might for example see a primitive form of AGI in 2027, a more capable form in 2028, and a more reliable form in 2030 (specific years and descriptors can vary). These might, for example, roughly correspond with OpenAI's five levels of AI: Level 3 (Agents), Level 4 (Innovators), and Level 5 (Organizations) (Metz, 2024). Still, this prediction offers us a baseline to reflect on in 2030.

Claim #2: AGI → ASI

Core Argument: *AGI will likely be used to improve its own design and develop ASI.*

If AGI is inevitable, and we proceed with our predicted timeline of 2028 to 2030, the next question becomes how long from AGI to ASI? The premise of the intelligence explosion follows that, once AI can conduct AI research as efficiently as an AI researcher, it may be able to iteratively improve its own design

and eventually bootstrap itself to ASI. This process is often called recursive self-improvement (RSI). Unless RSI is physically impossible, given the strong incentives to try, we believe developers will continually attempt to develop AI capable of RSI until somebody succeeds (barring regulations or other similar interventions). For our work, rather than viewing RSI as occurring only after a critical capability threshold is reached, we consider gradual contributions to AI R&D from AI in the years prior, i.e. the lead-up. One might consider an s-shaped curve that starts with ~100% human and ~0% AI contributions and ends with ~0% human and ~100% AI. Crossing the threshold at or near ~100% AI would constitute the critical transition, past which the fastest progress might be expected. We argue that many ML techniques and industry practices already show progress through this gradient. These techniques show a trend of AI becoming more participatory in AI development as humans gradually defer to AI's digital, scalable advantages. This progress is detailed below and depicted in **Figure 3**.

2012: Start of deep learning. Begins our RSI timeline at ~100% human and ~0% AI contributions.

2013: AutoML is introduced, demonstrating how AI can automate tasks like model selection, hyperparameter tuning, and feature engineering ([Thornton et al., 2013](#)).

2014: Synthetic data proliferates with generative adversarial networks (GANs). ([Goodfellow, 2014](#))

2016-17: Self-play becomes prevalent with AI playing games against itself ([Silver et al., 2016](#); [Silver et al., 2017](#)). Meta-learning grows in interest, enabling AI systems to optimize their own learning processes ([Finn et al., 2017](#)). Neural architecture search (NAS) shows potential for AI systems to automatically design network architectures ([Zoph & Le, 2016](#)).

2018: Self-supervised learning gains prominence, allowing models to learn from raw data without the need for human labels ([Devlin et al., 2018](#)).

2021: AI coding tools like GitHub Copilot ([Friedman, 2021](#)) and Codex ([Chen et al., 2018](#)) begin contributing to coding efficiency via autocompletion.

2022: Synthetic data becomes more widespread with diffusion models ([Yang et al., 2022](#)) and large language models (LLMs) ([OpenAI, 2022](#)).

2023: AI coding tools advance beyond autocompletion and into code generation (e.g. writing functions). AI starts aiding hardware development. Goals of automating AI alignment research ([OpenAI, 2023](#)) and maximizing AI in the loop during post-training for efficiency gains ([Sutskever, 2023](#)).

2024: AI shows signs of more complex reasoning abilities, as leading models score 55% on the SWE benchmark ([SWEBench](#)) and 78% on PhD-level science questions with reasoning models ([OpenAI, 2024](#)). Rapid progress on coding competitions. Passed ARC exam ([Chollet, 2024](#)) and shows early demonstrations of autonomy ([Anthropic, 2024](#); [Google, 2024](#)).

2025: Early versions of agents or autonomous systems start appearing ([OpenAI, 2025](#); [OpenAI, 2025](#)). Based on comments from many industry leaders (e.g. [Altman, 2025](#); [Amodei, 2025](#); [Hassabis, 2025](#)), more autonomous AI agents are expected in the future.

2026: Concrete progress on AI contributing to its own design. OpenAI launches GPT-5.3-Codex, their “first model that was instrumental in creating itself.” ([OpenAI, 2026](#)). Engineers at Anthropic state as much as 90% of the company's code is written by Claude ([Wong, 2026](#)). AI agents become more widespread ([Shroff, 2026](#)). Claude Mythos model shows newfound ability to find real-world, exploitable cybersecurity bugs ([Anthropic, 2026](#)).

As AI contributes more to R&D, we expect progress to accelerate, primarily due to AI's physical advantages. This would be unless deliberate ‘brakes’ were added for safety reasons (i.e., AI could be allowed more R&D control, but is prevented from doing so). If such self-imposed limitations were implemented, then the rate of progress might be somewhat controlled (i.e. a ‘controlled intelligence explosion’), such that the timeline from AGI to ASI may become arbitrary. However, given the incentives and pressures described, expecting this may be overly idealistic. Moreover, the Claude code leak in 2026 showed that a significant portion of code for the latest generation of Claude Code appears to be written by Claude ([Stetskov, 2026](#)). Hence, given the arms race dynamic in particular, we tend to expect that whatever is the fastest rate ASI can be developed is essentially the rate at which it will be developed.

Therefore, proceeding under the assumption that minimal or no brakes will be added, a powerful AGI may be allowed more access or control over its design more quickly, supported with human troubleshooting.

In this case, given AI’s digital advantages and how these would significantly hasten R&D progress, if AGI were to arrive in 2028, we estimate ASI would be developed within the next 1-3 years (2029-2031). In other words, we would expect a relatively ‘fast’ or ‘hard’ take-off, but we expect it to take at least a year to achieve due to practical limitations (e.g. real-world implementation time, finite compute available, etc.).

Accounting for the uncertainty of when AGI will be developed, if we consider our range of expected AGI timelines to be e.g. 2028-2030, this adjusts our ASI timeline prediction to a broader 2029-2033. We contend that assuming it will take longer than this due to any type of bottleneck (whether technical, infrastructural, financial, legal, cultural, etc.) may be needlessly high-risk.

Figure 3, Recursive Self-Improvement (RSI) as a Gradient: Flags indicate developments where AI shows ability to automate AI R&D tasks. Included are estimates corresponding to OpenAI’s five levels of AI: L1, Chatbots (2022); L2, Reasoning AI (2024); L3, Agents (2025-2026); L4, Innovating AI (2028?); L5, Organizational AI (2030?). L4 is selected as the best fit for the 50/50 point, given that if AI can innovate, then it can contribute to R&D decision-making, but this does not exclude skilled humans from contributing equally valuable insights. The specific placement of each level on this continuum is representative, not definitive.

Claim #3: ASI → Existential Risks

Core Argument: ASI would pose existential risks.

When claiming ASI would pose existential risks, we mean that to the same extent it is clear nuclear weapons pose existential risks, ASI would pose risks that are equally uncontroversial. There are many reasons why AI systems more intelligent than humans may be extremely dangerous for humanity. Given that literature already exists on this topic (e.g. [Bostrom, 2014](#); [Russell, 2019](#); [Bengio, 2023](#)), rather than extensively cover many reasons, we highlight three we find convincing, explore one in detail, then provide brief summaries of others.

Reason #1, ASI as an Existential Risk Multiplier: Nuclear weapons have shown that humans can create technology with existential risks, and as a significantly

more advanced technology, ASI would be far more dangerous. With superhuman abilities in far-reaching domains (e.g. hacking, robotics, R&D, etc.), ASI could theoretically both initiate other existential risks (deploy nuclear weapons, develop bioweapons, etc.) as well as pose new ones. Examples might include rogue ASI systems, the enforcement of ASI-stabilized surveillance states, or the development of novel weapons of mass destruction (WMDs). ASI might therefore become a central hub that many existential risks pass through. Moments like the Cuban Missile Crisis (1962) show how dangerously close humanity has come to a nuclear war, which many consider the clearest example of an existential risk. Since 1962, technology will have become much more powerful.

Reason #2, Self-Improvement: Self-improving AIs will likely be pursued for the competitive advantage of faster R&D cycles. Some CEOs have explicitly

pointed out that AIs are to be used for self-improvement: “AI systems are going to get so good that they help us make better next-generation systems” (Altman, 2024); “because AI systems can eventually help make even smarter AI systems, a temporary lead could be parlayed into a durable advantage” (Amodei, 2025). However, these approaches would likely be sensitive to initial conditions and could conceivably form an unstable feedback loop that may lead to unintended consequences.

Reason #3, Stacked Probabilities: To avoid existential risks, humanity must seemingly navigate difficult challenges across many domains (technical, geopolitical, social, etc.). If challenges are approximated as independent, such that each has its own probability of success, then the odds of avoiding existential risks becomes the product of these probabilities.

To explore Reason 3 in more detail, while the final probability depends on the number of challenges, modeling a single challenge to capture all risks would be trivial. It would likewise be a mistake to expect that solving any single challenge (e.g. ASI technical safety and alignment) guarantees solutions for all challenges necessary to avoid existential risks. Moreover,

modeling fewer challenges only increases the difficulty of each, as all major paths to existential risk must still be accounted for. Of course, ASI challenges are likely not truly independent as they build off one another, and since each is unique, the odds of solving each would vary. It is also an oversimplification to model complex challenges as simply pass/fail, when their outcomes realistically lie on a gradient. Still, the notion of multiplying probabilities to avoid existential risks demonstrates the difficulty ahead. A table of probabilities, as well as other arguments we find compelling, are summarized in Figures 4 and 5. More generally, given $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ independent challenges, for $0 \leq x \leq N$ challenges that fail:

$$(1) P(\text{challenge } i \text{ passes}) = p_i$$

$$(2) P(\text{all } N \text{ challenges pass}) = P(x = 0) = \prod_{i=1}^N p_i$$

$$(3) P(\text{at least 1 challenge fails}) = P(x \geq 1) = 1 - P(x = 0) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n p_i$$

N Challenges	Pessimistic		↔	Optimistic		$p_i = P(\text{Pass } i^{\text{th}} \text{ Challenge})$
	10%	25%	50%	75%	90%	
1	10%	25%	50%	75%	90%	$P(\text{Pass } N \text{ Challenges}) = \prod_{i=1}^N p_i$ <small>Note: calculations show simplified case where p_i is assumed constant across each challenge</small>
2	1%	6%	25%	56%	81%	
3	0.1%	2%	13%	42%	73%	
4	0%	0.4%	6%	32%	66%	
5 *	0%	0.1%	3%	24%	59%	
6	0%	0%	2%	18%	53%	
7	0%	0%	1%	13%	48%	
8	0%	0%	0.4%	10%	43%	
...	

(*) = Size of our framework.

Figure 4, Estimating the Odds of Avoiding Existential Risks:

Probability of avoiding existential risks over N challenges given a range of probabilities (p_i) of solving each challenge. Cumulative probabilities are shown for up to N = 8 distinct challenges; in our framework, we consider the case where N = 5.

Figure 5, Reasons Why ASI May Pose Existential Risks: Simplified arguments for how and why ASI may pose existential risks.

4. Framework

Framework Construction

Given the context detailed in our [Foundational Arguments](#), we proceed with our existential risk framework. We construct the framework as follows.

Step 1: Identify ASI Challenges

The wide range of ASI risks can make it difficult to specify what we aim to avoid. To manage this, we begin by first breaking down the goal of navigating ASI existential risks into a series of foreseeable sub-challenges, where if any of these sub-challenges were to have critical failure, the threat of existential risk would likely increase significantly. Solving all sub-challenges might therefore position humanity most promisingly to avoid existential risks.

To identify the optimal sub-challenges (from now on referred to simply as ‘challenges’), we start with those that reason to be unavoidable given the context specific to ASI. For example, in order for ASI to pose risks, it must first be developed, which indicates technical challenges. Distinct challenges that could fail independently might then be collated into a list that may vary by perspective. In our list, we identify five challenges that appear inevitable, globally consequential, and could have independent failure modes. Solving all five challenges might therefore

constitute broad guidelines for avoiding ASI existential risks (Table 2).

Challenges are identified based on what we currently know, so there may be others that we have overlooked or cannot foresee. Accordingly, solving all challenges would not guarantee avoiding existential risks, but would be a promising start. Given that the field is rapidly evolving, as we learn more about ASI, updating this list may be necessary.

Ensuring Independent Challenges: For a more comprehensive framework, we aim to avoid redundancy between our challenges. To verify that the challenges chosen are sufficiently independent, we consider whether each can reasonably fail regardless of the others succeeding. Of course, ASI’s various challenges are not truly independent, this is only a useful approximation. Any set of challenges would likely have interactions between them. To this end, a combination of failed challenges could lead to a combination of risk scenarios. Regardless, for our purposes, attempting to capture this level of detail would result in diminishing practical returns.

Defining Pass / Fail Criteria: How do we know if a challenge passes, fails, or is still to be determined? We contend that it seems unlikely that an ASI challenge passing hinges on a single event, but rather, there are many different smaller challenges or tests comprising the broader challenge that must be solved within a given percent success rate. The real-world criteria for

success are thus likely detailed, multifaceted, and may require domain-specific expertise for each challenge. Therefore, to determine if a challenge has successfully passed, a crowdsourced approach that receives input from the communities closest to each challenge would likely be most appropriate. For our purposes, it may be

easier to tell if a challenge has failed than if it has passed. As such, we focus on identifying various failure modes for each challenge. If a challenge fails, it should be covered by our failure modes. If none of the failure modes occur, then our model reasons that the challenge is likely passing.

Table 2, ASI Challenges: Seemingly inevitable challenges when avoiding ASI existential risks. Solving all five challenges tends towards an ASI future that is safe, fair, well-governed, healthy, and ethical.

Challenge	Reasoning
Technical Safety ASI must be safe.	For ASI to pose risks, it must first be created and thereby must be safely developed and maintained. This avoids existential AI safety risks, e.g. unaligned ASI, safety accidents, cybersecurity breaches, etc. These challenges are solved through research and engineering, like building safe nuclear facilities or spaceships.
Concentration of Power Power of ASI (<i>if controllable</i>) must not be overly concentrated	The premises of ASI allow for immense concentrations of power to form for a single nation, political party, or group of corporations. If this were to happen, then the broader fate of humanity would be in the hands of relatively few people. The profit-driven setting that ASI is being developed in also predates its origin and could very well influence the trajectory of future power dynamics.
International Governance ASI requires effective international governance.	Diplomacy is critical with ASI to avoid international conflict, and mutual agreements are likely necessary for more technologically advanced nations to coexist long-term. If these are not achieved, then an arms race, escalation, and potential conflict seem likely. Climate change also poses a global threat that all nations have a built-in interest in resolving collectively, particularly given ASI's vast energy needs.
Social Health Human society must not deteriorate.	Many risks to social health may operate on longer time scales (e.g. loss of human agency, social isolation, mental illness), resulting in more gradual, accumulative forms of existential risk (Kasirzadeh, 2025). Given ASI's anticipated far-reaching social impacts, social health must be explicitly protected.
Ethical Challenges Moral catastrophes must be avoided.	One can imagine scenarios in which earlier challenges are solved, but in morally problematic ways, as has been done with factory farming and industrial fishing, or sweatshops and child labor. Moral catastrophes with AI in particular may not be readily apparent, but on sufficient time scales, could presumably lead to backlash (e.g. if AI were to become conscious or have unacknowledged moral status).

Step 2: Prioritize Challenges

We prioritize challenges based on urgency, i.e. their time available to solve, impact on initial conditions, prerequisite nature for other challenges, etc. For example, if the technical aspects of safety and alignment are not solved, this would compromise basic preconditions that other challenges implicitly assume. R&D is also the activity physically creating ASI, and therefore naturally represents a further upstream encounter when navigating ASI existential risks. In this sense, our sequencing is intended to reflect the chronological order of the challenges encountered throughout the physical progression of ASI's development and deployment.

We understand that none of these challenges exist in isolation and that there may be unanticipated connections or overlap. We acknowledge that the reality is that all of these challenges affect each other and are in trade-off with each other, some more directly than others. Nevertheless, we believe each

challenge is unique enough from each other that they can roughly be modeled as independent, thus the linear progression. The reality is also not so simple as, once a challenge is solved, it never needs to be addressed again: this is merely a starting point for prioritization. We are not claiming these are the best ideas or the best model, only that this is a starting point (a 'Rev 01') for conversation about how to approach ASI existential risks more comprehensively. With those caveats, here are the five challenges we have identified.

Priority #1: ASI must be safely built.

This challenge represents the initial successful (i.e. safe, as intended, etc.) development of ASI itself. The goal is to ensure there are no technical or engineering failures that could lead to existential risks, like alignment failures, catastrophic safety accidents, or cybersecurity breaches. Building safe ASI therefore sets a physical initial condition that other challenges generally presume. This challenge might also have the

shortest timescale before critical consequences, making it highly time sensitive. In terms of risk vs. reward, this challenge is also uniquely significant. Failure could risk human extinction (CAIS, 2023), which would render all other challenges irrelevant. Meanwhile, solutions here may allow ASI to assist humanity with solving the remaining challenges. Solving these technical challenges for ASI alignment and safety thus becomes paramount, as they seem fundamental, time sensitive, and incredibly high stakes.

Priority #2: The power of ASI (if controllable) must not be overly concentrated.

It is often assumed that technical safety is the primary challenge for ASI existential risks. However, it is worth asking: safe according to whom? We contend that, after presuming the technology is developed in a safe manner, the next most likely and furthest upstream risk is the extreme concentrations of power that could form. Our second priority thus revolves around power and control. We differentiate safety from controllability, as ASI may be safe without being controllable, and vice versa. Accordingly, as ASI is being developed, who or what controls it? Intuitively, humans may not be able to control true superintelligence, as any restrictions, incentives, or other control strategies presumably could never be 100% foolproof and therefore could be exploited by ASI. If this were the case, such that ASI were effectively self-controlled, then this challenge may become irrelevant. Still, while it is counterintuitive to imagine that humans will be able to effectively control ASI, we cannot rule it out as impossible. In these scenarios, the next most likely entity in control is whoever built or funded the project. Their goals may vary, but is often profit for corporations, or geopolitical power for nations, both of which incentivize consolidating power. As such, this challenge could also be very time sensitive, for if power were allowed to concentrate early on, it could quickly become entrenched, which could lead to many dystopian futures. Resolving this tension thus becomes our second most urgent challenge for ASI.

Priority #3: ASI requires effective international governance.

Effective governance and regulations may still be valuable as part of earlier solutions for prior challenges, so they certainly need not wait. However, we presume that the urgency of these do not outweigh the urgency of technical safety and concentrations of power, given the risks of technical alignment, and the upstream nature of concentrations of power. We

contend that following these challenges, the next most likely source of ASI existential risk may stem from human conflict, either with or over ASI-enabled weapons. Given the R&D boosts one would expect from ASI, progress on militarized machines, lethal autonomous weapons, and perhaps even more science fiction scenarios like nanotechnology may present significant existential risk. Effective international governance thus becomes critical in building guardrails and global standards that humans must follow for ASI. Climate change also represents a global threat that likely requires international governance to resolve, with or without ASI. Given how energy intensive ASI efforts are likely to be, and the global scale of climate change, we thus include climate considerations here.

Priority #4: Human society must not deteriorate.

If the more immediate challenges prior are successfully handled, we can focus on risks that may not be as sudden but could be equally as harmful long-term: namely sociological and psychological ones. Importantly, none of the prior challenges focus directly on social health and sustainability, which are fundamental concepts in the broader context of existential risk. As such, our fourth challenge is intended to capture the long-term health of human society. As the fourth challenge in the framework, this target is intentionally much broader to capture more of the remaining risks that may slip past other challenges. Though it is the fourth challenge given its broader nature and longer timescales, it remains critical to include. It may be tempting to assume ASI processes that are technically shrewd, equitable and fair, and well-governed would thereby necessarily result in a healthy society. However, we find this to be an assumption, not a fact, as we see gaps. The clearest gap would be the mental health aspect of ASI, which is not addressed by earlier challenges, but is critical for a healthy society. Therefore, guarding against the general deterioration of human society, while exceedingly evident, is a challenge worth explicitly exploring.

Priority #5: Moral catastrophes must be avoided.

Though we list it last to avoid condescension, there is no priority ranking for avoiding moral catastrophes. The closest ranking would be '0', as this is a continuous challenge that underlies and permeates the others, having unique properties like the number zero. Many may argue that technical safety and alignment is the highest priority challenge, but we contend that ethical concerns precede even this. The clearest evidence of this is that when discussing AI alignment,

the question often asked is “aligned to whom?” suggesting there are ethical expectations for whoever aligns AI. The ongoing debate surrounding open-sourced vs closed-source AI also alludes to the early importance of ethics. But one might also consider if at a certain threshold, AI alignment encounters more complex moral questions. If for example, consciousness (e.g. [Butlin et al, 2023](#)) or digital minds were to emerge in AI systems, how might that affect the ethics of alignment? This consideration is dismissed by many, but importantly, we cannot disprove it as irrelevant. The ethics challenge, therefore, is constantly relevant as ASI is developed, as shown below by **Figure 6**.

Figure 6, Five ASI Challenges: Each challenge can be viewed as a filter that humanity must pass through. The ethics challenge stands unique as being constantly relevant.

After having prioritized each challenge and provided our rationale for why each is prioritized as such, we now explore each of the five challenges in more detail.

Challenge #1: Technical Safety and Alignment

The first challenge we identify as most likely to lead to existential risk is failing to solve technical alignment and safety for ASI. These are R&D challenges solved through research and technical engineering solutions. This is a very broad category that could lead to a variety of existential risk scenarios based on various technical failures. We identify seven different failure modes as seeming most plausible:

- 1.) **Goal Misspecification:** An ASI fails to align with broadly shared human values because its goals are specified incorrectly, incompletely, or through flawed proxies.
- 2.) **Deception:** An ASI appears aligned during training or oversight but develops hidden objectives that it later acts on. This failure mode is qualitatively different from most

because others generally presume good (pro-human) intentions from the ASI.

- 3.) **Loss of Control or Containment:** An ASI becomes difficult or impossible to reliably constrain, monitor, interrupt, or shut down. Reward function capture or recursive self-improvement gone awry could be two examples of loss of control.
- 4.) **Cybersecurity Failures:** Due to inadequate security measures, malicious actors are able to infiltrate, steal, manipulate, or weaponize ASI systems for harmful purposes.
- 5.) **Corrigibility or Value Rigidity:** An ASI may be initially aligned, yet fail to remain steerable, updateable, or responsive as contexts, goals, or values evolve over time.
- 6.) **Adverse Conditions:** An ASI may behave safely in expected settings, yet fail in novel, extreme, adversarial, or poorly understood conditions, (e.g. a power surge, extreme temperatures, flooding, etc.).
- 7.) **Emergent Coordination:** Multiple ASI systems or components interact in unforeseen ways, producing harmful system level dynamics that no single designer intended.

There may be additional failure modes outside of these seven for technical alignment and safety failures, but we believe these seven cover many of the main technical concerns for how ASI could pose existential risks. In terms of downstream effects of failing technical alignment, the most obvious risks are human extinction or an AI takeover. There could also be more indirect risk scenarios, like infrastructure collapse, or alteration of the biosphere. However, we keep our analysis focused on how failures could occur rather than the downstream effects, as it would be speculative to try to presume what specifically are the risks of each failure mode. Still, given the gravity of failing technical alignment and safety in general, we want to highlight how consequential failure here is. This is also often why this challenge is listed as the first or number one challenge to solve.

In terms of potential solutions, regulations that mandate a certain percentage of R&D funding is allocated to safety concerns would be a high-level solution. Perhaps there should be a required minimum ratio of people needed to focus on AI safety specifically for any major AI development projects. Perhaps safety and alignment research findings should be open source so that there is greater collective team effort towards AI safety. Third-party auditing of AI

models would also help ensure more objectivity in assessing model safety. There might also be lower-level solutions that mandate specific adversarial testing be done, but these sorts of prescriptions go beyond the scope of this paper (see [Existential Risk Observatory](#), n.d.). In general, having regulations or at least industry guidelines that pool resources into AI safety research are likely the greatest protection against ASI safety existential risks.

Lastly, it is worth considering the upside of solving these technical challenges. If humans are able to solve these technical challenges of ASI safety and alignment, in theory, this would enable humanity to have a superintelligence available that can help with solving the remaining four challenges. This is another reason why to list the technical challenges first, in addition to all the reasons stated before. We do not believe this ensures the remaining challenges are guaranteed to be solved, hence why we still cover them, but superintelligence would certainly help with finding solutions to the remaining four challenges.

Challenge #2: Concentration of Power

The second most probable existential risk we perceive for ASI boils down to a single group or stakeholder having a massively disproportionate amount of power relative to the average human on Earth. We contend that the simplest way to explore the existential risk space for concentration of power is to ask the question “Where is power most likely to concentrate?” Approaching this question, we see at least seven plausible outcomes where power could overly concentrate:

1. **First Mover Advantage:** Whoever develops ASI first is likely to have a great amount of power. This is especially true if the ASI can then be used to thwart others from creating it, as some of the technical safety literature suggests may be possible.
2. **Institutional Authority:** Whoever owns the monopoly on violence (i.e. the state and its military) may seize, nationalize, and monopolize control of ASI development.
3. **Compute Control:** Whoever owns the hardware stack may hold a disproportionate amount of power in the future, as this is a physical bottleneck of ASI development.

4. **Corporate Interests:** Whoever leads the largest AI or technology companies at the time of ASI stands to hold incredible power.
5. **Wealth as Access:** Whoever owns the most amount of money may be able to buy influence from one of the earlier mentioned centers of control.
6. **AI Knowledge and Expertise:** Whoever understands the most about AI stands to have a greater share of power, whether they be AI researchers, policymakers, or enthusiasts.
7. **Geography:** Even if none of the first six scenarios lead to extreme concentrations of power, it is very likely that certain countries (i.e. the United States and China) will likely have disproportionate amounts of power relative to other nations.

To be clear, it is not to say that if power is concentrated in one of these seven areas, that existential risk is guaranteed. However, we strongly believe that a great existential risk for ASI is extreme concentrations of power forming, and in that vein, these are the seven outlets we identify as most likely for this to occur. Example risk scenarios include ASI monopolies, extreme wealth inequality, and authoritarianism. Unrestricted corporations or nation states with ASI control could even lead to global economic collapse.

As far as potential solutions are concerned, having multiple groups working on ASI development simultaneously yet independently helps protect against the first mover advantage. In this same vein, having multiple companies or groups developing AI hardware helps protect against compute control being monopolized. Upholding democratic principles is a must to avoid authoritarian ASIs from being developed. Checks and balances between developers, investors, and state governments are likely a must to prevent any one group from holding too much power.

An important caveat for this challenge is the assumption that ASI can be controlled by humans. This may be a poor assumption, in which case, the concentration of power would manifest with the ASI itself (rather than its developers). However, these scenarios, while plausible, essentially mean that the future of humanity will be at the discretion of ASI, in which case, Challenge #1 with solving technical alignment remains the primary problem to solve.

Challenge #3: International Governance

Our third ASI challenge is achieving effective international governance and global standards for ASI. In the event that there is no international governance, the following failure modes may lead to existential risks:

- 1.) **Unregulated Arms Race:** Similar to the development of nuclear weapons, a race to the bottom with ASI safety standards could be existential in its risks.
- 2.) **Military Escalation & ASI War:** Global conflict such as World War 3, if propelled or enabled by ASI, could be existential in its scope. ASI may also develop novel WMDs that could pose existential risks if not globally regulated.
- 3.) **Defection by Malicious or Non-Compliant Actors:** International governance of ASI could be necessary to prevent malicious actors from developing ASI, as was the intention with nuclear weapons nonproliferation.
- 4.) **Environmental Catastrophe:** Given its global impact, climate change may be the greatest practical existential risk that ASI could make or break, given its energy cost.

Regarding existential risk scenarios, an unregulated arms race or militarization of ASI could lead to a variety of existential risks, including nuclear conflict, engineered pandemics, and large-scale cyberattacks. If not governed effectively, ASI might also allow for complete surveillance states and massive human rights violations. On the environmental side, if there are no regulations regarding ASI's development and use cases, there could be climate collapse, atmospheric destruction, air pollution, and many more existential risks. Resource scarcity such as a freshwater crisis or food insecurity could also be relevant environmental risks. Thus, having effective international regulations for ASI is critical for global well-being.

Regarding potential solutions, the most important would be establishing shared global safety standards. Major countries and frontier labs need baseline rules for what counts as unacceptable development or deployment. Safety measures such as minimum safety testing, dangerous capability evaluations, incident reporting, security standards, and global red lines would have to be established. Another needed solution would be verification and monitoring systems. There needs to be some way to monitor frontier training runs,

compute clusters, chip supply chains, model evaluations, and major incidents. A third solution might be compute governance. Since frontier ASI development is likely bottlenecked by chips, cloud infrastructure, and energy, global regulations can target those chokepoints. This may entail licensing large training runs, tracking advanced chip flows, monitoring large scale compute usage, and requiring reporting above certain thresholds. A fourth solution could be international treaties or binding agreements. The most obvious analog is nuclear nonproliferation. States may need formal agreements on prohibited uses, emergency protocols, information sharing, nonproliferation of certain capabilities, and coordinated responses to dangerous developments. A fifth solution would be establishing an international regulatory body to enforce the aforementioned solutions. This body would be analogous to the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), but be specific to ASI. Another potential solution would be open-sourcing AI safety research, so that all parties involved in ASI development could contribute to and benefit from pertinent AI safety solutions.

Of course, all of these are easier said than done. The unfortunate reality is that the incentives for any one group pursuing ASI do not necessarily align with slowing down for regulations. Actors with the most power to cooperate may have the strongest incentive not to. Verification is also difficult: GPU clusters provide some visibility, but given that ASI is largely a software endeavor, it may be difficult to confirm exactly what each actor is building without direct cooperation. There is also the issue of geopolitical mistrust that is difficult to overcome, and the difficulty of enforcing international laws. Lastly, and perhaps most importantly, the pace of progress of AI and thereby ASI development may move faster than institutions can adapt.

Still, it is worth gathering the ideas and attempting to raise awareness of ASI challenges and corresponding existential risks. In sum, the main risks of lacking international governance for ASI are international arms races and potential military conflict. With that, we move onto our next key ASI challenge, which relates to social health and well-being.

Challenge #4: Social Health

Our fourth challenge is the broadest and seeks to capture all of the major dynamics through which ASI

could threaten human society in manners outside of technical safety and alignment, concentration of power, and international governance. For example:

- 1.) **Economic Automation:** ASI has real potential to automate eventually every job. Universal basic income or another social safety net will likely be needed to support people whose work is displaced by ASI.
- 2.) **Displacement and Disempowerment:** If ASI is nearly always the optimal path for decision-making, this could displace humans from decision-making. In the same vein, overreliance on ASI could lead to enfeeblement.
- 3.) **Meaning and Purpose:** If ASI is able to solve all the major problems of society, there is a risk of nihilism and purposelessness for many people, particularly if most jobs become automated.
- 4.) **Atrophy of Human Relationships:** If ASI is personable to everyone, the isolation and atomization seen today with technology could continue to an unprecedented degree.
- 5.) **Epistemic Breakdown:** Loss of shared reality. ASI could theoretically enable hyper-personalized, persuasive, and synthetic information environments that fragment objective truth.
- 6.) **Cultural Homogenization:** ASI-generated content may lead to consolidation of cultural norms and loss of diversity.
- 7.) **Social Lock-in, Stagnation:** Similar to corrigibility failures described for technical safety, if ASI is not sufficiently adaptable in its design, a certain vision of society could become effectively locked into place, leading to social stagnation.

These seven ideas are almost certainly not all-encompassing. While this challenge may allow more time for solutions, it may have the largest scope and most varied failure modes, thereby making it one of the more difficult challenges. However, solving these challenges is fundamentally necessary for a long-term healthy future between humans and AI.

In terms of potential solutions, the most important solution is increasing awareness and education of AI and its risks to the broader public. Many of these social

risks of ASI would best be mitigated by having a better-informed public. Unlike nuclear weapons or bioweapons, understanding more about the nature of AI may be extremely important in mitigating its social risks. To this end, having public figures who are very knowledgeable about AI share their perspectives could be hugely beneficial (e.g. Andrej Karpathy, Ilya Sutskever, Dario Amodei, Sam Altman, etc.). Additionally, on the design front, including safeguards in the design process to protect against overreliance on ASI could be hugely beneficial. One example for how this could be done is by having AI models ask the user questions, rather than just giving answers or completing tasks. This allows the user more cognitive input on the direction of the conversation, though it would have to be balanced with practicality. Regarding epistemic breakdown, having ground truth data is extremely important (e.g. it is a fact that World War II lasted from 1939 to 1945, ants have six legs, etc.), however, determining what the ground truth is for certain questions is naturally difficult. Still, assuming that the ASI is trained on historically and scientifically accurate data, there should not in theory be a loss of shared reality. For cultural homogenization, getting training data from less-spoken languages is critical to preserve cultural diversity. For atrophy of human relationships, having limits for how long one can interact with an ASI might be a crude but effective way of preventing people from over relying on the ASI for social connection. Overall, however, the main solutions we see for the social risks of ASI are awareness and education.

Challenge #5: Ethics

The final challenge we list here is perhaps the most important apart from technical alignment. As was discussed, technically aligned to whom? The ethical challenges of ASI cannot be overstated. Of the five challenges listed, the ethical challenges may be most analogous to the thumb of the hand. It's the shortest finger, but inarguably the most important.

The following are existential questions to consider regarding the ethical challenges of ASI:

- 1.) **AI Consciousness:** While we do not know if AI can become conscious or sentient, if it can (or even, if it already is), this opens up a variety of critical ethical questions. Because we do not know definitively either way, exercising precaution would seem prudent.
- 2.) **Responsibility:** If something goes wrong with ASI, the question of legal responsibility

becomes immense. Is it the ASI's fault, the developer's fault, a licensor's fault, or the user's fault? ASI legislation will be critical to determine responsibility in different contexts.

- 3.) **Transparency:** Given the stakes and anticipated impacts of ASI on daily life, the broader public is likely owed more transparency than they are owed e.g. transparency for nuclear weapons.
- 4.) **Fairness:** Minimizing bias with ASI will be incredibly important to live in a fair and equitable society.
- 5.) **Open-Source:** We believe that ethical ASI may likely have to err towards open-source in order to be transparent and fair. There may otherwise be too great of a concentration of power.

On a fundamental level, the most important question from the ethical side seems to do with the ASI's moral status itself. Fortunately, if this is the case, it seems reasonable to suspect that a superintelligent AI would be able to effectively advocate for itself on this issue in particular. However, humanity cannot afford to defer all moral issues to ASI, hence, it would be ideal to have made some progress on this issue prior to achieving superintelligence. Likewise could be said for the other issues described of responsibility, transparency, and fairness.

While perhaps not an inherent requirement, we believe that in general, open source with ASI would lead towards safer long-term outcomes. Moments like the Claude code leak (e.g. [Ramonov, 2026](#)) show just how vulnerable closed-source initiatives are to becoming public knowledge due to a single honest mistake. The fragility of these approaches we believe show an underlying flaw in the viewpoint that closed source is actually safer. In human psychology, it is often not advised to repress difficult thoughts or emotions due to unintended consequences. One might argue that there is a similar risk profile in attempting to close source superintelligence. On the surface, it may seem reasonable as a way to deter bad-faith actors from accessing superintelligence. However, beneath the surface, this approach encodes secrecy and greater pressure placed on those with access to the superintelligence, which in the long run, may lead to sudden leaks that defeat the purpose of closed source to begin with. Closed source may also tend towards

concentrations of power worsening, whereas open source in theory helps level the playing field.

5. Discussion

The implications of the arguments and framework outlined are striking. By our estimate, humanity may have roughly five years to grapple with five significant challenges. The statistical argument outlined is particularly sobering. Even if one presumed humanity has a 90% chance of solving ASI alignment, and that solving this challenge boosts the odds of success on the remaining four challenges to 95%, this still suggests an only 73.3% chance of solving all five challenges. Modeling such numbers is also extremely optimistic. This is not to lose hope, only to stay grounded in the challenges that lie ahead. Given how much rests on the technical alignment being solved, it is worth considering whether or not sufficient resources are currently being allocated to AI safety research. Without regulations, it is understandably difficult to prioritize AI safety given the commercial pressures companies are under. And regulations are likely not to keep pace with the rapid rate of AI development, hence, it is easy to get caught in a loop, where there are no easy solutions. Nevertheless, we must try.

The first practical step is raising awareness of superintelligence specifically: not of AI's development, or even AGI, but of the concept of ASI's development more explicitly. This would help significantly in relaying to people the gravity of the situation that lies ahead. The second practical step is raising awareness of the five challenges outlined here: technical safety, concentration of power, international governance, social health, and ethical challenges. Reiterating this list often and having it become part of the public dialogue about AI/ASI might go a long way towards building solutions for these challenges. Conversely, skipping between each of the five challenges based on personal resonance will continue to splinter the dialogue about ASI, such that people talk past each other about whichever issue they hold as most significant.

In terms of the number of challenges we modeled, we understand that some people may argue there are only e.g. three challenges: technical, governance, and ethics. We believe that such a model underplays the challenge of concentration of power greatly, and

assumes that the ethics and governance piece would inherently cover social health. Meanwhile, others may argue that there should be more challenges. For our work, we tried to keep it to the minimal number possible, which is how we concluded with five challenges. There could be more challenges, e.g. climate change could be great enough existential risk to warrant its own challenge, which would bring us up to six. The economic challenges of handling job displacement could be considered its own challenge as well, which would bring us to seven. In our model, however, the economic challenges are covered by social health, and the environmental challenges are covered by international governance.

There are a number of significant limitations with this research that are worth acknowledging. First and foremost, modeling ASI existential risks into a series of five challenges humanity must contend with is an oversimplification of a much more complex reality. To that end, modeling each challenge as pass/fail and sequencing the challenges linearly are also oversimplifications. In reality, the challenges must be solved in parallel, and success vs failure lies more on a gradient than it does a binary switch. Nevertheless, these assumptions help with managing model complexity, which is extremely useful for improving communicability, as well as to avoid overfitting the model to a more complex framework that feigns understanding of something extremely complex. Furthermore, the number one goal of this research is to increase awareness of ASI existential risks without overcommitting to a single type of risk, like technical safety or geopolitical competition, as many conversations today about ASI risks do. To that end, even if the model represented is an oversimplification, it still covers a wider, more diverse range of ASI existential risks than a narrower focused paper that highlights only one type of challenge.

Lastly, given this paper's focus on ASI existential risks, one might be tempted to infer that we are against developing superintelligence, but this would be false. Given the challenges that humanity faces with climate change, geopolitical tensions, and other risks, we find it not only preferable to develop superintelligence, but necessary. Moreover, the potential upsides that exist for ASI will propel development forward regardless, so there is less need to emphasize these. Still, given how much we have explored the existential risk space, it is important to state directly that we are still in favor of developing superintelligence, despite its risks.

6. Conclusion

We have made the case that superintelligence may arrive between the years 2029 and 2033, given that underestimating the rate of future progress poses asymmetrical risks. We have outlined five major challenges for ASI (technical safety, concentration of power, international governance, social health, and ethical challenges), where if any fail, this could lead to existential risk with ASI. Future research directions could include delving deeper into the failure modes of each challenge or the existential risks of failing each challenge. It may also be that there are additional challenges that were not covered by our main five that require exploration. Overall, the goal of this work has been to consolidate ASI existential risks into a single cohesive framework that coherently prioritizes each challenge. Doing so may aid in grounding conversation about ASI existential risks in a way that helps minimize the probability of such risks.

7. References

- A Right to Warn about Advanced Artificial Intelligence*. (June 4, 2024). <https://righttowarn.ai/>
- Acemoglu, D., & Restrepo, P. (2018). Artificial Intelligence, Automation, and Work. In *The Economics of Artificial Intelligence: An Agenda* (pp. 197–236). University of Chicago Press. <https://www.nber.org/books-and-chapters/economics-artificial-intelligence-agenda/artificial-intelligence-automation-and-work>
- AI 2027*. (April 3, 2025). <https://ai-2027.com/>
- AI Index* | Stanford HAI. (n.d.). Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://hai.stanford.edu/ai-index>
- AI Is Wall Street's Modern Gold Rush. Here's How Investors Are Placing Their Bets*. - WSJ. (Feb 2, 2025). <https://www.wsj.com/tech/ai/ai-wall-street-investments-companies-0baba8d9>
- Alex Kantrowitz. (2025, January 23). *Google DeepMind CEO Demis Hassabis: The Path To AGI, Deceptive AIs, Building a Virtual Cell* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yr0GiSgUvPU>
- Allyn, B. (2025, January 14). "The New York Times" takes OpenAI to court. ChatGPT's future could be on the line. *NPR*. <https://www.npr.org/2025/01/14/nx-s1-5258952/new-york-times-openai-microsoft>
- Altman, S. (2023, February 24). *Planning for AGI and beyond. OpenAI*. <https://openai.com/index/planning-for-agi-and-beyond/>
- Altman, S. (2024, September 23). *The intelligence age*. <https://ia.samaltman.com/>
- Altman, S. (2025, January 5). *Reflections*. <https://blog.samaltman.com/reflections>
- Altman, S. (2025, June 10). *The gentle singularity*. <https://blog.samaltman.com/the-gentle-singularity>
- Amodei, D. (2024, October). *Machines of Loving Grace*. <https://darioamodei.com/essay/machines-of-loving-grace>
- Amodei, D. (2025, January). *On DeepSeek and Export Controls*. <https://darioamodei.com/post/on-deepseek-and-export-controls>
- Announcing The Stargate Project*. (2025, January 21). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/announcing-the-stargate->

- [project/](#)
- Anomaly, J. (2014, February 7). *What's Wrong With Factory Farming? Public Health Ethics*, 8(3), 246–254. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/phe/phu001>
- Anthropic raises \$30 billion in Series G funding at \$380 billion post-money valuation. (February 12, 2026). <https://www.anthropic.com/news/anthropic-raises-30-billion-series-g-funding-380-billion-post-money-valuation>
- Armstrong, S., Bostrom, N., & Shulman, C. (2016). Racing to the precipice: A model of artificial intelligence development. *AI & SOCIETY*, 31(2), 201–206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-015-0590-y>
- Aschenbrenner, L. (2024, June). *Situational awareness: The decade ahead.* <https://situational-awareness.ai/>
- Asgari, E., Montaña-Brown, N., Dubois, M., Khalil, S., Balloch, J., Au Yeung, J., & Pimenta, D. (2025). A framework to assess clinical safety and hallucination rates of LLMs for medical text summarisation. *Npj Digital Medicine*, 8(1), 274. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01670-7>
- Bellan, R. (2025, July 9). Microsoft shares \$500M in AI savings internally days after cutting 9,000 jobs. *TechCrunch*. <https://techcrunch.com/2025/07/09/microsoft-shares-500m-in-ai-savings-internally-days-after-cutting-9000-jobs/>
- Bengio, Y. (2023, June 24). *FAQ on catastrophic AI risks.* <https://yoshuabengio.org/en/blog/faq-catastrophic-ai-risks>
- Bengio, Y., Hinton, G., Yao, A., Song, D., Abbeel, P., Darrell, T., Harari, Y. N., Zhang, Y.-Q., Xue, L., Shalev-Shwartz, S., Hadfield, G., Clune, J., Maharaj, T., Hutter, F., Baydin, A. G., McIlraith, S., Gao, Q., Acharya, A., Krueger, D., ... Mindermann, S. (2024). Managing extreme AI risks amid rapid progress. *Science*, 384(6698), 842–845. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adn0117>
- Bostrom, N. (2002). Existential risks: Analyzing human extinction scenarios and related hazards. *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, 9(1), 1–31. <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:827452c3-fcba-41b8-86b0-407293e6617c>
- Bostrom, N. (2012). The Superintelligent Will: Motivation and Instrumental Rationality in Advanced Artificial Agents. *Minds and Machines*, 22(2), 71–85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-012-9281-3>
- Bostrom, N. (2013). Existential Risk Prevention as Global Priority. *Global Policy*, 4(1), 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.12002>
- Bostrom, N. (2014). *Superintelligence: Paths, dangers, strategies.* Oxford University Press. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2014-48585-000>
- Bridge, A. (2024, June 21). *SoftBank CEO talks up artificial super intelligence ambitions.* Yahoo Finance. <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/softbank-ceo-talks-firms-ai-021434154.html>
- Brown, T. B., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Agarwal, S., Herbert-Voss, A., Krueger, G., Henighan, T., Child, R., Ramesh, A., Ziegler, D. M., Wu, J., Winter, C., ... Amodei, D. (2020). *Language Models are Few-Shot Learners* (arXiv:2005.14165). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.14165>
- Bubeck, S., Chandrasekaran, V., Eldan, R., Gehrke, J., Horvitz, E., Kamar, E., Lee, P., Lee, Y. T., Li, Y., Lundberg, S., Nori, H., Palangi, H., Ribeiro, M. T., & Zhang, Y. (2023). *Sparks of Artificial General Intelligence: Early experiments with GPT-4* (arXiv:2303.12712). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.12712>
- Butlin, P., Long, R., Elmoznino, E., Bengio, Y., Birch, J., Constant, A., Deane, G., Fleming, S. M., Frith, C., Ji, X., Kanai, R., Klein, C., Lindsay, G., Michel, M., Mudrik, L., Peters, M. A. K., Schwitzgebel, E., Simon, J., & VanRullen, R. (2023). *Consciousness in Artificial Intelligence: Insights from the Science of Consciousness* (arXiv:2308.08708). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.08708>
- Center for AI Safety, Scale AI, & HLE Contributors Consortium. (2026). A benchmark of expert-level academic questions to assess AI capabilities. *Nature*, 649(8099), 1139–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09962-4>
- Chan, J. S., Chowdhury, N., Jaffe, O., Aung, J., Sherburn, D., Mays, E., Starace, G., Liu, K., Maksin, L., Patwardhan, T., Weng, L., & Mađry, A. (2025). *MLE-bench: Evaluating Machine Learning Agents on Machine Learning Engineering* (arXiv:2410.07095). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.07095>
- Chen, M., Tworek, J., Jun, H., Yuan, Q., Pinto, H. P. de O., Kaplan, J., Edwards, H., Burda, Y., Joseph, N., Brockman, G., Ray, A., Puri, R., Krueger, G., Petrov, M., Khlaaf, H., Sastry, G., Mishkin, P., Chan, B., Gray, S., ... Zaremba, W. (2021). *Evaluating Large Language Models Trained on Code* (arXiv:2107.03374). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2107.03374>
- Chervonyi, Y., Trinh, T. H., Olšák, M., Yang, X., Nguyen, H., Menegali, M., Jung, J., Kim, J., Verma, V., Le, Q. V., & Luong, T. (2025). *Gold-medalist Performance in Solving Olympiad Geometry with AlphaGeometry2* (arXiv:2502.03544). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.03544>
- Chui, M., Hazan, E., Roberts, R., Singla, A., Smaje, K., Sukharevsky, A., Yee, L., & Zimmel, R. (2023, June). *The economic potential of generative AI: The next productivity frontier.* McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/tech-and-ai/our-insights/the-economic-potential-of-generative-ai-the-next-productivity-frontier>
- Cihon, P., Schuett, J., & Baum, S. D. (2021). Corporate Governance of Artificial Intelligence in the Public Interest. *Information*, 12(7), 275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12070275>
- CNBC Television. (2025, January 23). *Scale AI CEO Alexander Wang on U.S.-China AI race: We need to unleash U.S. energy to enable AI boom* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x9EkI9Izd38>
- Chollet, F. (2024, December 20). OpenAI o3 breakthrough high score on ARC-AGI-Pub. *ARC Prize*. <https://arcprize.org/blog/oai-o3-pub-breakthrough>
- Companies ranked by Market Cap—CompaniesMarketCap.com.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://companiesmarketcap.com/>
- DeepSeek-AI, Guo, D., Yang, D., Zhang, H., Song, J., Wang, P., Zhu, Q., Xu, R., Zhang, R., Ma, S., Bi, X., Zhang, X., Yu, X., Wu, Y., Wu, Z. F., Gou, Z., Shao, Z., Li, Z., Gao, Z., ... Zhang, Z. (2025). DeepSeek-R1 incentivizes reasoning in LLMs through reinforcement learning. *Nature*, 645(8081), 633–638. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09422-z>
- Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019). *BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding* (arXiv:1810.04805). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1810.04805>
- Diaz, J. (2025, July 10). A recent high-profile case of AI hallucination serves as a stark warning. *NPR*. <https://www.npr.org/2025/07/10/nx-s1-5463512/ai-courts-lawyers-mypillow-fines>
- Dr Jordan B Peterson [@jordanbpeterson]. (2024, July 22). *My conversation with @elonmusk. Live today at 3pm ET.* <https://t.co/RyaZFmvC8i> [Tweet]. Twitter.

- <https://x.com/jordanbpeterson/status/1815427698703090085>
- Dubber, M. D., Pasquale, F., & Das, S. (Eds.). (2020). *The Oxford Handbook of Ethics of AI*. Oxford University Press. https://www.google.com/books/edition/The_Oxford_Handbook_of_Ethics_of_AI/8PQTEAAAQBAJ?hl=en
- Dwarkesh Patel. (2023, October 26). *Shane Legg (DeepMind Founder)—2028 AGI, superhuman alignment, new architectures* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kc1atfJkijU>
- Elon Musk [@elonmusk]. (2024, December 23). @chamath It is increasingly likely that AI will superset the intelligence of any single human by the end of 2025 and maybe all humans by 2027/2028. Probability that AI exceeds the intelligence of all humans combined by 2030 is ~100%. [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://x.com/elonmusk/status/1871083864111919134>
- Eye on AI. (2023, March 15). *The Mastermind Behind GPT-4 and the Future of AI | Ilya Sutskever* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SjhIlw3Iffs>
- Faisal, A. A., Selen, L. P. J., & Wolpert, D. M. (2008). Noise in the nervous system. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 9(4), 292–303. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2258>
- Finn, C., Abbeel, P., & Levine, S. (2017). *Model-Agnostic Meta-Learning for Fast Adaptation of Deep Networks* (arXiv:1703.03400). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1703.03400>
- Friedman, N. (2021, June 29). Introducing GitHub Copilot: Your AI pair programmer. *The GitHub Blog*. <https://github.blog/news-insights/product-news/introducing-github-copilot-ai-pair-programmer/>
- Garrick, J., & Buck, M. (2020). WHISTLEBLOWER RETALIATION CHECKLIST: A NEW INSTRUMENT FOR IDENTIFYING RETALIATORY TACTICS AND THEIR PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACTS AFTER AN EMPLOYEE DISCLOSES WORKPLACE WRONGDOING. *Crisis, Stress, and Human Resilience: An International Journal*, 2(2), 76–93. <https://www.crisisjournal.org/article/17219-whistleblower-retaliation-checklist-a-new-instrument-for-identifying-retaliatory-tactics-and-their-psychosocial-impacts-after-an-employee-discloses-w>
- Gates, B. (2023, March 21). *The age of AI has begun*. GatesNotes. <https://www.gatesnotes.com/The-Age-of-AI-Has-Begun>
- Gemini Deep Research—Your personal research assistant*. (n.d.). Gemini. Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://gemini.google/us/overview/deep-research/?hl=en>
- Geoff Hinton, AI's Most Famous Researcher, Warns Of 'Existential Threat' From AI. (2023, May 4). <https://www.forbes.com/sites/craigsmith/2023/05/04/ge-off-hinton-ais-most-famous-researcher-warns-of-existential-threat/>
- Geoffrey Hinton on the promise, risks of artificial intelligence | 60 Minutes—CBS News. (2024, June 16). <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/geoffrey-hinton-ai-dangers-60-minutes-transcript/>
- Goldman, S. (2024, August 26). *OpenAI's AGI safety team has been gutted, says ex-researcher*. Fortune. <https://fortune.com/2024/08/26/openai-agi-safety-researchers-exodus/>
- Good, I. J. (1966). Speculations concerning the first ultraintelligent machine. In F. L. Alt & M. Rubinoff (Eds.), *Advances in Computers* (Vol. 6, pp. 31–88). Elsevier. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2458\(08\)60418-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2458(08)60418-0)
- Goodfellow, I. J., Pouget-Abadie, J., Mirza, M., Xu, B., Warde-Farley, D., Ozair, S., Courville, A., & Bengio, Y. (2014). *Generative Adversarial Networks* (arXiv:1406.2661). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1406.2661>
- Google DeepMind. (2024, July 25). *AI achieves silver-medal standard solving International Mathematical Olympiad problems*. <https://deepmind.google/blog/ai-solves-imo-problems-at-silver-medal-level/>
- GPT-4. (2023, March 14). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/gpt-4-research/>
- Ha, A. (2025, April 12). OpenAI co-founder Ilya Sutskever's Safe Superintelligence reportedly valued at \$32B. *TechCrunch*. <https://techcrunch.com/2025/04/12/openai-co-founder-ilya-sutskevers-safe-superintelligence-reportedly-valued-at-32b/>
- Hello GPT-4o. (2024, May 13). OpenAI. Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://openai.com/index/hello-gpt-4o/>
- Hendrycks, D., Mazeika, M., & Woodside, T. (2023). *An Overview of Catastrophic AI Risks* (arXiv:2306.12001). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.12001>
- Hendrycks, D., Schmidt, E., & Wang, A. (2025). *Superintelligence Strategy: Expert Version* (arXiv:2503.05628). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2503.05628>
- Hidden Costs: Nuclear Weapons Spending in 2024—ICAN*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://www.icanw.org/hidden-costs-2024-global-nuclear-weapons-spending>
- Introducing ChatGPT*. (2022, November 30). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/chatgpt/>
- Introducing computer use, a new Claude 3.5 Sonnet, and Claude 3.5 Haiku*. (2024, October 22). <https://www.anthropic.com/news/3-5-models-and-computer-use>
- Introducing deep research*. (2025, February 2). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-deep-research/>
- Introducing GPT-5.3-Codex*. (2026, February 5). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-gpt-5-3-codex/>
- Introducing GPT-5.5*. (2026, April 23). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-gpt-5-5/>
- Introducing OpenAI*. (2015, Dec 11). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-openai/>
- Introducing OpenAI o3 and o4-mini*. (2025, April 16). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-o3-and-o4-mini/>
- Introducing Operator*. (2025, January 23). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-operator/>
- Introducing Superalignment*. (2023, July 5). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-superalignment/>
- Jumper, J., Evans, R., Pritzel, A., Green, T., Figurnov, M., Ronneberger, O., Tunyasuvunakool, K., Bates, R., Židek, A., Potapenko, A., Bridgland, A., Meyer, C., Kohl, S. A. A., Ballard, A. J., Cowie, A., Romera-Paredes, B., Nikolov, S., Jain, R., Adler, J., ... Hassabis, D. (2021). Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature*, 596(7873), 583–589. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2>
- Kaplan, J., McCandlish, S., Henighan, T., Brown, T. B., Chess, B., Child, R., Gray, S., Radford, A., Wu, J., & Amodei, D. (2020). *Scaling Laws for Neural Language Models* (arXiv:2001.08361). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2001.08361>
- Kasirzadeh, A. (2025). Two types of AI existential risk: Decisive and accumulative. *Philosophical Studies*, 182(7), 1975–2003. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11098-025-02301-3>
- Kaur, G. (2025, June 18). Sam Altman says Meta offered \$100 million bonuses to OpenAI employees. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/business/sam-altman-says-meta-offered-100-million-bonuses-openai-employees-2025-06-18/>
- Knight, W. (2020, February 21). Defeated Chess Champ Garry Kasparov Has Made Peace With AI. *Wired*. <https://www.wired.com/story/defeated-chess-champ-garry-kasparov-made-peace-ai/>

- Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., & Hinton, G. E. (2012). ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 25. <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2012/hash/c399862d3b9d6b76c8436e924a68c45b-Abstract.html>
- Learning to reason with LLMs. (2024, September 12). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/learning-to-reason-with-llms/>
- LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., & Hinton, G. (2015). Deep learning. *Nature*, 521(7553), 436–444. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>
- Lower costs and 100+ new languages coming to Gemini 1.5. (2024, August 1). Google Cloud Blog. <https://cloud.google.com/blog/products/ai-machine-learning/lower-costs-more-languages-for-gemini-on-vertex>
- Lu, C., Lu, C., Lange, R. T., Foerster, J., Clune, J., & Ha, D. (2024). *The AI Scientist: Towards Fully Automated Open-Ended Scientific Discovery* (arXiv:2408.06292). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.06292>
- Maginative. (2024, September 21). *Sam Altman and Mike Sievert Fireside Chat at T-Mobile Capital Markets Day 2024* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0sOe4iF3aUM>
- Meitner, L., & Frisch, O. R. (1939). Disintegration of Uranium by Neutrons: A New Type of Nuclear Reaction. *Nature*, 143(3615), 239–240. <https://doi.org/10.1038/143239a0>
- Meta to invest up to \$65 bln in capital expenditure this year. (2025, January 24). Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/technology/meta-invest-up-65-bln-capital-expenditure-this-year-2025-01-24/>
- Metz, C., & Isaac, M. (2025, June 10). Meta Is Creating a New A.I. Lab to Pursue ‘Superintelligence.’ *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/06/10/technology/meta-new-ai-lab-superintelligence.html>
- Metz, R. (2024, July 11). OpenAI Scale Ranks Progress Toward ‘Human-Level’ Problem Solving. *Bloomberg.com*. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-07-11/openai-sets-levels-to-track-progress-toward-superintelligent-ai>
- Millett, P., & Snyder-Beattie, A. (2017). Existential Risk and Cost-Effective Biosecurity. *Health Security*, 15(4), 373–383. <https://doi.org/10.1089/hs.2017.0028>
- Milmo, D. (2024, July 14). US financial watchdog urged to investigate NDAs at OpenAI. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/article/2024/jul/14/us-financial-watchdog-urged-to-investigate-ndas-at-openai>
- Morris, C. OpenAI resignations are reaching an alarming level. Here are 11 key people who have left. (2024, May 17). *Fast Company*. <https://www.fastcompany.com/91126785/openai-resignations-are-reaching-an-alarming-level-here-are-11-key-people-who-have-left>
- Morris, M. R., Sohl-Dickstein, J., Fiedel, N., Warkentin, T., Dafeo, A., Faust, A., Farabet, C., & Legg, S. (2023). *Levels of AGI for Operationalizing Progress on the Path to AGI* (arXiv:2311.02462). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.02462>
- Nellis, S. (2024, March 1). Nvidia CEO says AI could pass human tests in five years. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/technology/nvidia-ceo-says-ai-could-pass-human-tests-five-years-2024-03-01/>
- O'Brien, M. (2024, April 4). Tech companies want to build artificial general intelligence. But who decides when AGI is attained? *AP News*. <https://apnews.com/article/agi-artificial-general-intelligence-existential-risk-meta-openai-deepmind-science-ff5662a056d3cf3c5889a73e929e5a34>
- OpenAI announces leadership transition. (2023, November 17). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/openai-announces-leadership-transition/>
- OpenAI Charter. (n.d.). OpenAI. Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://openai.com/charter/>
- OpenAI LP. (2019, March 11). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/openai-lp/>
- OpenAI raises \$122 billion to accelerate the next phase of AI. (2026, March 31). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/accelerating-the-next-phase-of-ai/>
- Ord, T. (2020). *The precipice: Existential risk and the future of humanity*. Hachette Books. <https://www.hachettebookgroup.com/titles/toby-ord/the-precipice/9780316484893/>
- Our latest health AI research updates. (2023, March 14). Google. <https://blog.google/innovation-and-ai/technology/health/ai-llm-medpalm-research-thecheckup/>
- Ouyang, L., Wu, J., Jiang, X., Almeida, D., Wainwright, C. L., Mishkin, P., Zhang, C., Agarwal, S., Slama, K., Ray, A., Schulman, J., Hilton, J., Kelton, F., Miller, L., Simens, M., Askell, A., Welinder, P., Christiano, P., Leike, J., & Lowe, R. (2022). *Training language models to follow instructions with human feedback* (arXiv:2203.02155). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.02155>
- Owen, D. (2024, August 27). *Automation of AI R&D: Researcher Perspectives*. https://epoch.ai/files/Interviewing_AI_researchers_on_automation_of_AI_R_D.pdf
- Prescott, M. J. (2010). Ethics of primate use. *Advances in Science and Research*, 5(1), 11–22. <https://doi.org/10.5194/asr-5-11-2010>
- Ramonov, S. (2026, April 2). *Comprehensive Analysis of Claude Code Source Leak!* <https://www.sabrina.dev/p/claude-code-source-leak-analysis>
- Rein, D., Hou, B. L., Stickland, A. C., Petty, J., Pang, R. Y., Dirani, J., Michael, J., & Bowman, S. R. (2023). *GPQA: A Graduate-Level Google-Proof Q&A Benchmark* (arXiv:2311.12022). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.12022>
- Rhodes, R. (1995). *Dark Sun: The Making Of The Hydrogen Bomb*. Simon & Schuster. <https://www.simonandschuster.com/books/Dark-Sun/Richard-Rhodes/9780684824147>
- Robinson, M. (2025, July 1). The establishment of an international AI agency: An applied solution to global AI governance. *International Affairs*, 101(4), 1483–1497. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/ia/iaf105>
- Russell, S. *Human compatible: Artificial intelligence and the problem of control*. (2019). <https://cmc.marmot.org/Record/b60478391>
- Sadek, T., Stanley, K. D., Smith, G., Marcinek, K., Cormarie, P., & Gunashekar, S. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence Impacts on Privacy Law*. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA3243-2.html
- Safe Superintelligence Inc. (n.d.). Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://ssi.inc>
- Sagan, S. D. (2011). The Causes of Nuclear Weapons Proliferation. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 14, 225–244. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-052209-131042>
- Schafer, B. (2026, March 31). *SpaceX Absorbed xAI at a Combined \$1.25 Trillion Valuation. Here Is What That Means for the Coming IPO*. The Motley Fool. <https://www.fool.com/investing/2026/03/31/spacex-absorbed-xai-at-a-combined-125-trillion-val/>
- Schmid, S., Lambach, D., Diehl, C., & Reuter, C. (2025). Arms

- Race or Innovation Race? Geopolitical AI Development. *Geopolitics*, 30(4), 1907–1936. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2025.2456019>
- seremot. (2024, December 13). *Ilya Sutskever: "Sequence to sequence learning with neural networks: what a decade"* [Video]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1yvBqasHLZs>
- Shroff, L. (2026, February 17). *AI Agents Are Taking America by Storm*. The Atlantic. <https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/2026/02/post-chatbot-claude-code-ai-agents/686029/>
- Siegel, D. (1997). The Impact of Computers on Manufacturing Productivity Growth: A Multiple-Indicators, Multiple-Causes Approach. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 79(1), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003465397556548>
- Silver, D., Huang, A., Maddison, C. J., Guez, A., Sifre, L., van den Driessche, G., Schrittwieser, J., Antonoglou, I., Panneershelvam, V., Lanctot, M., Dieleman, S., Grewe, D., Nham, J., Kalchbrenner, N., Sutskever, I., Lillicrap, T., Leach, M., Kavukcuoglu, K., Graepel, T., & Hassabis, D. (2016). Mastering the game of Go with deep neural networks and tree search. *Nature*, 529(7587), 484–489. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16961>
- Silver, D., Schrittwieser, J., Simonyan, K., Antonoglou, I., Huang, A., Guez, A., Hubert, T., Baker, L., Lai, M., Bolton, A., Chen, Y., Lillicrap, T., Hui, F., Sifre, L., van den Driessche, G., Graepel, T., & Hassabis, D. (2017). Mastering the game of Go without human knowledge. *Nature*, 550(7676), 354–359. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24270>
- Soga, M., & Gaston, K. J. (2018). Shifting baseline syndrome: Causes, consequences, and implications. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 16(4), 222–230. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1794>
- Sora is here*. (2024, December 9). OpenAI. <https://openai.com/index/sora-is-here/>
- Sriram, A., & Bajwa, A. (2025, April 14). Nvidia to produce AI servers worth up to \$500 billion in US over four years. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/technology/artificial-intelligence/nvidia-says-working-with-partners-make-ai-supercomputers-us-2025-04-14/>
- Stanislaw Ulam writes that John von Neumann once explained the coming singularity... (n.d.). Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://scribili.ca/Google%2B20131213-John-von%20Neumann-Singularity.html>
- Statement on AI risk*. (2023, May). Center for AI Safety. <https://aistatement.com>
- Stetskov, D. (2026, April 1). *Claude Code's Source: 3,167-Line Function, Regex Sentiment*. <https://techtrenches.dev/p/the-snake-that-ate-itself-what-claude>
- Stribling, D., Xia, Y., Amer, M. K., Graim, K. S., Mulligan, C. J., & Renne, R. (2024). The model student: GPT-4 performance on graduate biomedical science exams. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 5670. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-55568-7>
- Sukharevsky, A., Kerr, D., Hjartar, K., Hämäläinen, L., Bout, S., Di Leo, V., & Dagorret, G. (2025, June). Seizing the agentic AI advantage. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/quantumblack/our-insights/seizing-the-agentic-ai-advantage>
- Suno | *AI Music Generator*. (n.d.). Suno. Retrieved April 18, 2026, from <https://suno.com/>
- SWE-bench Leaderboards*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2026, from <https://www.swebench.com/>
- Thornton, C., Hutter, F., Hoos, H. H., & Leyton-Brown, K. (2013). Auto-WEKA: Combined selection and hyperparameter optimization of classification algorithms. *Proceedings of the 19th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, KDD '13*, 847–855. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2487575.2487629>
- Toosi, A., Bottino, A., Saboury, B., Siegel, E., & Rahmim, A. (2021). A brief history of AI: How to prevent another winter (a critical review). *PET Clinics*, 16(4), 449–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpet.2021.07.001>
- Turco, R. P., Toon, O. B., Ackerman, T. P., Pollack, J. B., & Sagan, C. (1983). Nuclear Winter: Global Consequences of Multiple Nuclear Explosions. *Science*, 222(4630), 1283–1292. <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.222.4630.1283>
- Unaligned AI. (n.d.). Existential Risk Observatory. Retrieved April 24, 2026, from <https://www.existentialriskobservatory.org/unaligned-ai/>
- UNDP (Ed.). (2025). *A matter of choice: People and possibilities in the age of AI*. United Nations. <https://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/global-report-document/hdr2025reporten.pdf>
- United States Joint Economic Committee. (2026, April 9). *GDP update*. <https://www.jec.senate.gov/public/index.cfm/republican/s/gdp-update>
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, L., & Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 30. <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2017/hash/3f5ee243547dee91fbd053c1c4a845aa-Abstract.html>
- Vinge, V. (1993). The coming technological singularity: How to survive in the post-human era. In *Vision 21: Interdisciplinary Science and Engineering in the Era of Cyberspace* (NASA Conference Publication CP-10129). NASA Lewis Research Center. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/19940022856>
- von Neumann, J., & Kurzweil, R. (2012). *The Computer and the Brain*. Yale University Press. https://www.google.com/books/edition/The_Computer_and_the_Brain/hvPAUX0glAYC?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=The+Computer+and+the+Brain+1958&pg=PP2&prints=ec=frontcover#v=onepage&q=The%20Computer%20and%20the%20Brain%201958&f=false
- Wagenaar, W. A., & Sagaria, S. D. (1975). Misperception of exponential growth. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 18(6), 416–422. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03204114>
- Wong, M., Shroff, L. (2026, April 3). *Silicon Valley Is in a Frenzy Over Bots That Build Themselves*. The Atlantic. <https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/2026/04/ai-industry-self-improving-bots/686686/>
- WSJ Events. (2025, January 21). *Inside Anthropic's race to build a smarter Claude and human-level AI* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=snkOMOjiVOK>
- Yang, L., Zhang, Z., Song, Y., Hong, S., Xu, R., Zhao, Y., Zhang, W., Cui, B., & Yang, M.-H. (2022). *Diffusion Models: A Comprehensive Survey of Methods and Applications* (arXiv:2209.00796). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.00796>
- Yudkowsky, E. (2013). *Intelligence explosion microeconomics* (Technical Report 2013-1). Machine Intelligence Research Institute. <https://intelligence.org/files/IEM.pdf>
- Zoph, B., & Le, Q. V. (2017). *Neural Architecture Search with Reinforcement Learning* (arXiv:1611.01578). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1611.01578>